

Using SEO techniques Google Panda to Improve the Website Ranking

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Abstract—SEO is the process of taking actions to gain unique traffic from search engines your ranking and place on a search engine website depends on user queries which in turn on what your web page have done for Search Engine Optimization. The Web search engine is faced with a much difficulties, problems in maintaining or enhancing the quality of their performance. These problems are either uncommonly to this domain or novel variants of problems that have been studied in the literature. And the same time webmaster website web page owner facing problem to learn the search engines update policy and page ranking and index systems learn how and that thing keep important to enhance to quality of website web page to top ranking our studies focus new Google panda 4.0 policy update in search engine new Google panda 4.0 is extremely important for and quickly improve ranking of single original fresh website web page to it is keywords in top ranking in search engines. Your client has a website with the same copy used in multiple places push for immediate removal you notice this if you have you post a press release to multiple websites, for examples. The webmasters are more likely to be caught and penalized for duplicate content with the new panda update it is time to start editing and it causes their website to be completely blocked from ranking at all or at the extremely least cause their content to rank far lower than it.

Keywords— Search Engine Optimization, Search Engine Marketing, Pay Per click Google Panda, SEO Techniques

I. INTRODUCTION

Search engine optimization (SEO) has been around since the mid-1990s. Although search algorithms have changed and evolved, causing various SEO tactics to rise and fall in favor, one thing has remained constant: the purpose of search engine optimization.[1]. The purpose of SEO is to help search engines, in response to a search query, find and rank your Web content higher than competing sites. It works as a process and set of techniques for boosting a website's ranking on Google and other big search engines in natural (i.e., organic or unpaid) search results. Referring to this basic purpose and definition of SEO is helpful because it reminds us that SEO shows how humans behave (query, scan and click) and how search engines behave (crawl, index, process, calculate relevancy and retrieve). Understanding both is important for optimal effectiveness in your SEO endeavors [2].

II. AIM OF THE THEORY RESEARCH

A. Theoretical History Background

Let look back on what occur over the past two decades 1994 2014, Brain Pinkerton creates the first Crawler to index entire website and page its generates a list of 25 website its called web Crawler. Excite is kind of a big deal in the 90s. It launches in 1993 and purchases WebCrawler in 1996, but eventually stops gathering its own listings in 2001. Launched in 1994, Lycos in one of the first crawler-based search engines. By 1997 it has indexed over 60 million documents. It eventually outsources its search results to Alltheweb.

Yahoo is still powered by humans with crawler- based results from partner's only showing if no human powered result exists. Danny Sullivan launches search engines watch to discuss all things search in 1997. Google launches and uses Page Rank to rank websites more accurately. Google! BETA 1998. Danny Sullivan Launches the 1st Conference just for Search in the conference topics covered include:

- Designing, Search Engine Friendly websites Tips for those who build sites to make them more search engine friendly and top into traffic naturally.
- Meta Tags Different experts explain their strategies to writing meta tags.
- Doorway Pages Learn the pros and cons of creating content precisely optimized for search engines

In 1999, Search Engines Optimizations still have problem with Search engine updates. AltaVista re launches its website and changes its algorithm. Lot's of websites disappear. Google launches AdWords as CPM model in 2000 and Google has also released a Page Rank Toolbar so SEO can now record their Page rank. Google gets into contextual Advertising with Google AdSense. In 2003.

Rand Fishkin launches SEOMOZ and quickly turns it into one of the industry authorities on all things search. And Aaron Wall releases the 1st PDF version of Seobook, one of the best known books on the subject of search. In 2005, Google releases the no follow tag to combat blog spam which is supported by both MSN and Yahoo. Google Launches Google Analytics, giving SEOs an easy way to analyze and track the performance of their campaigns. Later on xml Sitemaps launch and are supported by all of the major search engines. Google Suggest launches. This gives SEOs another tool to help with keyword research. In 2008 and in 2009, social networks are helping to provide real time results for users google want to make sure its index can provide fresher result. Google Panda 1st time released in 2011 with new algorithm affect that website that is

making content farms. Google launches Panda its aim to prevent site with low quality content from acquiring top-tier ranking its forces SEOs to put more focus on the quality of content they were published Google Panda confirmed a major panda update that likely included both an algorithm and data refresh. About 7.5 of English Languages queries were affected while Matt Cutts said it began rolling out on 5/20 our data strongly suggests it start earlier Panda 4.0 may 19 2014 [3],[4]

III. THE POPULAR SEARCH ENGINE RESULT JULY 2014

The most popular Search Engines as a plagiarist from our eBizmba website rank averages of this website's Alexa Global Traffic Rank and United kingdom of America Traffic Rank form both complete and Qunactast estimate for website with limited data.

A. Search Engine results July, 2014

	Google 1 eBizMba rank 1100000 000 estimated average monthly visitors 1 compete rank 1 Quantcast rank 1 Alexa website Rank July 2014
	Bing 15 eBizMba rank 35000 000 estimated average monthly visitors 5 compete rank 19 Quantcast Rank 22 Alexa Website Rank July 2014
	Yahoo 18 eBiamBa rank 300000 000 estimated average monthly visitors 8 compete rank 28 Quantcast rank NA Alexa Website Rank July 2014
	Ask 25 eBizMba rank 245000 000 estimated average monthly visitors 14 compete rank 31 Quantcast rank 31 Alexa website rank July 2014
	Aol 245 eBizMba Rank 125000 000 estimated average monthly visitors 250 compete rank 240 Quantact Rank NA Alexa Website July 2014
	Wow 271 eBizMba rank 100000 000 estimated average monthly visitors 20 compete rank 26 Quantcast rank 767 Alexa Website Rank July 2014
	Webcrawler 511 eBizMba Rank 65000 000 estimated average monthly visitors 100 compete rank 759 Quantcast

	rank 674 Alexa Website Rank Mywebsearch 545 eBizMba Rank 60000 000 Estimated average monthly visitors 105 compete Rank 1124 Quantcast Rank 405 Alexa Website Rank July 2014
	Infospace 892 eBiamBa Rank 24000 000 estimated average monthly visitors 66 compete rank 500 Quantcast rank 2110 Alexa website rank July 2014
	Info.com 1064 eBizmBa Rank 13500 000 Estimated average monthly visitors 378 compete Rank 877 Quantcast Rank 1938 Alexa website Rank July 2014
	Duckduckgo2153 eBizamBa Rank 13000 000 estimated average monthly visitors 2323 Compete Rank 3479 Quantcast Rank 658 Alxea Website Rank July 2014
	Blekko 2280 eBiazmBa Rank 12500 000 Estimated average monthly visitors 862compete Rank 1461 Quantcast rank 658 Alexa Website rank July 2014
	Contenka 2402 eBizmba Rank 11000 000 Estimated average monthly visitors 200 compete Rank 2500 Quantact Rank 4505 Alexa Website Rank July 2014
	Dogpile 2421 eBazimBa Rank 10500 00 Estimated average Monthly Visitors 2734 Compete Rank 1446 Quantact Rank 3084 Alex Website Rank July 2014
	Alhea 4300 eBaizmBa Rank 7500,000 Estimated average Monthly visitors 451 compete Rank 1225 Quantast Rank 11255 Alex Website rank July 2014

B. Google Panda 4.0 update

According Google Respective define at this time few things you totally must know none of them are difficult, but they help you stay on top of your game, impress your clients and earn that promotion.

- Diligently watch for duplicate content
- If your client has a website with the same copy used in multiple places push for immediate removal
- Never publish blog posts that you find on other sites
- Remember long content is better than shorter
- Focus on writing and placement quality, not quantity

C. Search Engine Marketing (SEM)

The term Search Engine Marketing was introduced by Sullivan to refer the variety of activities involved in performing SEO, managing PPC listings, submitting websites to different directories, and developing online marketing strategies for businesses, organizations, and individuals. Further, Sullivan (2010) Defined SEM as a form of web marketing that seek method include SEO, PPC, contextual advertising, digital asset optimization and paid inclusion (PI) Moreover Curran (2004).

D. Pay Per Click (PPC)

Pay per Click was designed as a technique of creating revenue for search engines. Over the past 16 years users have become familiar to search engines offering free services for which are not prepared to pay, PPC or pay for placement is used to explain a variety of overlapping practices that in essence refer to linking person website to specific keywords for payment Moxley 2004. As a result future target market will use in a search Curran 2004. It is also important for webmasters to search the possible keywords that may be used in a search for their specific product or service. PPC may become costly as advertisers are locked in an ongoing competition for popular keywords as Pay per Click suggests advertisers also have to pay for every click they receive via that sponsored link Jansen and Schuster 2011.[5],[6]

IV. SEARCH ENGINE OPTIMIZATION STRATEGY

Several websites rank well in the search engine; on the other hand, some website cannot be founded by the search engines, thus, how to making a website to be at a high rank. 1st need to learn the basic information about search engine optimization strategy. Search Engine Optimization analysis of your website conducted by professional Search Engine Optimization advisor to highlight, chances for the improvement of ranking, keyword research SEO keyword Research your targeted domain and identify keywords and phrases which help to achieve good results. SEO link building Search engines and optimization, link building method is used on your website will allow to achieve higher ranking. [7], [8].

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our research study aim in this paper has presented the results of a be trained in the Search Engine Optimization techniques use by SEO Google Panda Experts to rank this website and web page number one in research results. Several Search Engine optimization experts use old domain and short domain for higher rankings, and it is true that is a successful method. Listing website in social media and web directory is techniques as more successful Search Engines Optimizations

Google panda now don't allow web pages, index duplicate and copy paste content of website and only fresh and perfect content can easy index in google research results. Back linking is the best way to improve the website web page ranking easy and fast way and index it faster then other website and selecting keyword for website and focus on that keyword to ranking website it is easy to check keyword competitor then start website keyword ranking that improve to website get top ranking on research engines results.[10]

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented some challenging problem faced by existing search engines. There are other wealthy areas of research related to the search engine we did not touch on for instances, there are challenging issues our study aims to highlight issues and problem for website owner, webmaster how top rank their website using google panda search engine update to enhance their website web page ranking in top position.

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